

Identifying large scale structures in the solar wind with a simple derivative analysis

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Keypoints

- The study presents a simple derivative-based technique for identifying boundaries of solar wind structures in time series data, using second derivatives and fluctuation thresholds to isolate coherent features.
- This method is versatile and can be applied to data from various spacecraft and observatories, demonstrated through its use on multiple datasets from the April 2023 geomagnetic storm.
- By helping to consistently identify structures like CMEs, fast solar wind flows, and interaction regions, the technique enhances our ability to interpret solar wind dynamics and assess their impact on Earth's magnetosphere.

Abstract

Understanding the structure and evolution of solar wind drivers is critical for interpreting their impact on Earth's space environment. We introduce a simple yet powerful derivative-based technique for identifying coherent structures in time series data, applicable from any spacecraft and observatory. By calculating the second derivative and applying a simple threshold, this method helps pinpoint boundaries of solar wind structures such as CMEs, fast flows from coronal holes,

and stream interaction regions. We demonstrate its versatility across multiple datasets from the April 2023 geomagnetic storm, an event marked by complex solar activity and intense magnetospheric response. Our approach enhances the interpretation of solar wind dynamics and supports more consistent identification of geo-effective structures, offering a valuable tool for future observational studies and space weather forecasting.

Plain Language Summary

We have developed a simple method to help identify large-scale structures in solar wind data, such as eruptions and fast speed streams from the Sun. It works by looking how much data fluctuates on time, using the second derivative. This helps pinpoint where one structure ends and other begins. We tested the method on data from the April 2023 geomagnetic storm, and found it useful for analyzing different types of solar wind activity. This approach could make it easier for scientists to interpret space weather data and improve forecasts of how solar wind events affect Earth.

1 Introduction

In April 2023, we witnessed the first intense geomagnetic storm of Solar Cycle 25 [55]. Geomagnetic storms (GSs) are disturbances in Earth's magnetosphere that can lead to electrical and satellite disruptions, as well as the production of auroras. The event was classified as an intense geomagnetic storm (IGS) as it reached SYM-H values below -100 nT [81]. It was associated with the release of several flares [13] and coronal mass ejections [CMEs, 68, 76, 70, 82] originated from an active region [AR, 77] surrounded by coronal holes [CHs, 11, 12, 79].

Generally, the presence of ARs near CHs indicates complex solar magnetic field topologies, which may nest various magnetic structures, including filaments - accumulations of cold, dense plasma above polarity inversion regions [1, 90]). CMEs with helical magnetic field configurations - known as flux-ropes or magnetic clouds (MCs) [5, 6, 39, 20, 16, 26] - have been directly linked to filament eruptions [46]. Structures that were also implicated in the April 2023 storm.

Once in the interplanetary medium CMEs are referred to as interplanetary CMEs [ICMEs, 17, 35], and it is important to note that ICMEs may be complex structures, potentially related to multiple CMEs rather than a single one. During propagation, they may interact with each other, either preserving their individual magnetic configurations or merging to form more intricate magnetic field structures.

Furthermore, ICMEs may interact with fast solar wind flows originating from CHs, influencing their dynamic evolution and potentially causing deflection [18]. CMEs with MCs tend to deflect toward the ecliptic plane more than non-MC CMEs [87] and CMEs are more geo-effective when propagating along or being deflected toward the ecliptic plane [80]. Additionally, fast flows from CHs may

evolve into streams - known as stream interaction regions [SIRs, 63] - and/or corotating interaction regions [CIRs, 57, 58, 59] when observed across multiple solar rotations, as these fast flows overtake slower preceding solar wind flows.

Both, ICMEs and SIRs/CIRs can be associated with the formation of shock waves [7, 4, 36, 85, 54], which further influence the geo-effectiveness of these solar wind drivers.

So far, it is not possible to predict when events like the April storm will occur, nor to determine the number of eruptions or fast flows (or their combinations) that may be involved, their stages of evolution, or their consequences on Earth.

Although numerous statistical analyses [40, 79, 21, 69, 44, 47, 67] and numerical simulations [34, 33, 31, 45, 42, 66, 2, 56] have been conducted to investigate these phenomena, much work remains in interpreting observational data. The April storm, for instance, has been extensively studied - not only in terms of the solar wind evolution [e.g., 84, 55] but also regarding its influence on the magnetosphere and even deeper layers of Earth's atmosphere [e.g., 38, 91, 48, 15, 24, 75, 41, 60, 88, 78].

A key aspect of these investigations is the identification of large-scale velocity and magnetic field structures - such as CMEs/ICMEs, fast flows originating from CHs, and SIRs/CIRs, or any resulting interactions among them - propagating through the solar wind and ultimately disturbing Earth's magnetosphere. This task heavily depends on the interpreter's approach and the specific research objectives.

These differences play a major role in understanding the evolution of the solar wind, CMEs/ICMEs, fast flows originating from CHs, SIRs/CIRs, and any complex structures resulting from their interactions. They are also crucial in identifying the key factors that determine the geo-effectiveness of such events. The most intense geomagnetic storms are associated with complex interactions among different structures, particularly between CMEs [43].

Studies - and our understanding of their geo-effectiveness - could be significantly improved if there were a consensus on how data is interpreted, specially when identifying the various solar wind structures that may play a major role in solar wind evolution.

In this work, we present a simple analysis that can be applied to any time series to aid in determining structure boundaries. The method involves calculating the second derivative of a time series measured by any spacecraft or observatory and using the resulting fluctuations as *pass-band* filters. We assume that a large-scale coherent structure exhibits a consistent level of fluctuations; therefore, when the fluctuation value remains below a selected threshold, consecutive data points are considered part of the same structure. The choice of threshold is related to the size of the structure being identified in the data.

We introduce the derivative analysis through its application to various datasets that recorded solar wind conditions and geomagnetic activity during the April storm.

We begin by reviewing previous efforts to analyze and understand this event (Section 2). In Section 4, we revisit the remote-sensing observations and, based on EUV imagery, demonstrate that the event was associated with a filament

eruption originating from a highly complex magnetic field configuration involving a dynamic AR surrounded by multiple CHs. We, then present white-light images to identify the corresponding CME, along with in situ observations from two different spacecraft.

In Section 5, we detail the proposed derivative analysis applied to the solar wind velocity time series from OMNI [37]. To demonstrate the general applicability of our method, Section 6 showcases its performance across multiple datasets related to the April storm, including: 1) white-light images from the *Solar and Heliospheric Observatory* [SOHO, 14] and the *Solar TERrestrial RElations Observatory* [STEREO-A, 32]; 2) speed, density and magnetic field data from OMNI and the STEREO-A; 3) the Disturbance Storm Time $D_{ST}/SYM-H$ [81] index; and 4) cosmic ray counts measured by various neutron monitor detectors. Finally, Section 7 presents our conclusions.

2 Identifying Large scale Structures - Previous Attempts

Typically, the identification of solar wind (SW) structures relies on detecting specific signatures in the solar wind measurements. For instance, ICMEs are often identified using the criteria described by [92] while SIRs/CIRs follow the guidelines of [27]. Some signatures are similar across different structures; others are strict, meaning they are only detectable when the structures impact the instruments in a particular direction, configuration or evolutionary stage. In some cases, expected signatures may not appear at all.

Efforts have been done to produce catalogs to assist the research community. For ICMEs, examples include *Wind* ICME catalog [51, 52, 53], the Near-Earth Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections list [61], and the CCMC CME Scoreboard service among others. For SIRs/CIRs, notable catalogs include those by [28, 30, 22, 10, 29, 64]. For shocks, useful resources include the following websites: <https://lweb.cfa.harvard.edu/shocks/>, <http://www.ipshocks.fi/database>, http://www.ssg.sr.unh.edu/mag/ace/ACELists/obs_list.html#shocks, https://izw1.caltech.edu/ACE/ASC/DATA/Shocks/shocks_all.html and (https://stereo-ssc.nascom.nasa.gov/data/ins_data/impact/level3/).

Some efforts even aim to combine different structures, such as the ICME-CME-SSS catalog by the George Mason University [https://http://solar.gmu.edu/heliophysics/index.php/ICME-CME-SSS_catalog, 89].

Nevertheless, structure identification remains a subjective process, particularly when determining the structure boundaries and their relationships with various solar wind features and the interactions. As seen in the case of the April storm, there is no consensus on the characterization of the solar wind.

For example, [55] provided a detail analysis of remote sensing and in situ observations to study the propagation of *a single eruption* from Sun to Earth. Their findings suggested that the geo-effectiveness of the ICME was enhanced due to its interaction with flows originating from CHs, which led to deflection

and rotation of the ICME. By comparing magnetic hodograms from the *Wind* and STEREO-A spacecraft within the magnetic cloud, they observed an almost 180° rotation in the Y-Z plane.

[84] developed several analytical models to reconstruct *a single magnetic cloud* with non-circular cross-sections and a distorted magnetic field axis. By assuming distortion within the ICME, they proposed different scenarios to explain the discrepancies between the datasets from the two spacecraft. Notably, this investigation did not consider the interaction between the ICME and the fast solar wind flows originating from CHs.

It is important to note that in both studies, the start and end times of the magnetic cloud were determined subjectively by the respective authors. For example, in *Wind*, [55] identified the magnetic cloud from 2023 April 24, 01:55 to 15:50 UT, while [84] defined it from 2023 April 24, 04:12 to 13:51 UT. The ICME *Wind* Catalog lists the interval as 2023 April 24, 00:46 to 19:54 UT. In STEREO-A, [55] reported the magnetic cloud from 2023 April 23, 23:40 UT to April 24, 14:15 UT, whereas [84] defined it from 2023 April 24, 06:59 to 14:44 UT.

In other example, [24] described auroral activity resulting from the arrival of a *single ICME*. Using data from the *Wind* spacecraft, they characterized the storm driver as a shock arriving on 2023 April 23 at 16:58 UT, followed by a sheath region and a MC spanning from 2023 April 24 at 01:21 to 22:44 UT. [83] adopted this structural characterization to investigate the geo-electric field variations during the storm.

Similarly, [78] studied the low-latitude auroras, assuming the arrival of a shock on 2023 April 23 at 17:35 UT, followed by a sheath region and a MC observed from 2023 April 24 at 01:00 to 22:00 UT.

These studies illustrate how authors define ICME boundaries, with only one investigation reporting interaction between the ICME and fast solar wind flows. Such characterization significantly influences the interpretation of the event - for instance, the magnetic field configuration of the ICME, the solar wind composition, its fluctuations, and its evolution.

Moreover, some investigations overlook the sources of the solar wind and instead focus on specific plasma conditions that trigger features of the April storm [41, 15, 91, 38]. For example, [38] associated the storm with multiple eruptions and structures that collectively shape the solar wind conditions. Rather than analyzing individual structures, they treated the solar wind as *one complex structure*, identifying correlations not only with the magnetic field intensity, its Z-component, and velocity, but also with temperature.

[48] briefly discussed the event as the result of a weak ICME interacting with a SIR, focusing on the resulting ionospheric storm. Both [38] and [88] examined Earth's ionospheric response under the assumption of a shock arrival on 2023 April 23 at 17:45 UT followed by an ICME. Meanwhile, [91] linked an extreme auroral electrojet spike to a pulse in the solar wind dynamic pressure, without addressing the solar wind structures or their relationship to the pulse.

3 Observations

In this work, we use insitu measurements from the *Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory* [32, STEREO] mission and OMNI data [37], which combines solar wind parameters collected by the *Advanced Composition Explorer*

4 The 2023 April Geomagnetic Storm

On 2023 April 21 at 17:28 UT, a filament, initially observed near active region AR 13283 at S20W15 (233", -249") and a coronal hole with its centroid located at (-4", -726"), was released into the interplanetary medium. The filament was visible across multiple EUV channels, particularly in AIA 304 Å (see *right* panel of Figure 1) while the coronal hole was observed in AIA 193 Å and the active region in HMI (Figure 2).

Figure 1: *Left*: Locations of Parker Solar Probe, BepiColombo, Solar Orbiter (SolO), STEREO-A, and Earth from 2023 April 21 to April 27, shown in Heliocentric Earth Ecliptic (HEE) coordinates. *Right*: AIA 193 Å image showing the brightening of the filament prior to its eruption, beginning on 2023 April 21 at 17:27 UT.

At the time of the eruption, STEREO-A was located at heliographic coordinates (-10.293°, -5.964°) in the Heliocentric Earth Ecliptic (HEE) coordinate system (*left* panel of Figure 1).

In the WL images, the corresponding CME became visible starting on 2023 April 21 at 18:00 UT. In Figure 3, we present the COR2-A and C2 images with the grid of the 3D CME configuration overlaid, as obtained using the Gradual Cylindrical Shell model [GCS, 74, 73, 72].

In the SOHO/LASCO CME Catalog https://cdaw.gsfc.nasa.gov/CME_list/, the eruption is reported as a Halo-CME [e.g., 25, 19] launched on 2023 April 21 at 18:12 UT with a linear speed of 1284 km s⁻¹ and a mass of 1.5 × 10¹⁶ g. It is also listed in the CACTus CME [65] C2 <https://www.sidc>.

Figure 2: *Left*: AIA 193 Å image with coronal hole boundaries overlaid in *cyan*. *Right*: HMI image of the Sun showing several ARs on the solar surface. The filament eruption occurred near AR 13283, adjacent to the southern CH visible in the AIA 193 Å image.

be/cactus/catalog.php and the COR2-A <https://secchi.nrl.navy.mil/cactus/> catalogs. In the C2 catalog, the CME was identified on 2023 April 21 at 18:12 UT with a speed of $821 \pm 375 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ while in the COR2-A catalog, it was recorded on 2023 April 21 at 18:53 UT with a speed of $892 \pm 185 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. In both catalogs, the CME is characterized as Type III, meaning it has an angular width of $da > 180^\circ$.

The ICME reached STEREO-A (-10.173° , -5.822°) on 2023 April 23 at 12:00 UT, and Earth later that day at 18:00 UT. In Figure 4, we show the solar wind in situ observations from OMNI. From *top to bottom*, the panels display: *first panel*, the temperature (T, in *gray*) and the magnetic field magnitude ($|B|$; *second panel*, *black*) and radial (R, *navy*), tangential (T, *cyan*) and normal (N, *purple*) components of the magnetic field and the velocity (*third panel*), *fourth panel*, the magnitude of the velocity ($|V|$, *black*), the number density (N, *gray*), fifth panel the flow (P_{FLOW} , *black*) and magnetic (P_{MAG} , *navy*) pressures and the sixth panel SYM-H index (in *black*) and the cosmic ray count rate from different observatories. In this figure, we display data from eight observatories: ATHN, NANM, AATB, BKSJ, JUNG, LMKS, IRK2, YKTK. These sites represent a range of effective vertical cutoff rigidities. However, the full analysis was conducted using 32 observatories; additional details are provided in the Appendix. The three *purple* vertical lines indicate the arrival (2023 April 23 16:54 UT), start (2023 April 24 00:46 UT) and end (2023 April 24 19:54 UT) times of the magnetic cloud, as reported in the ICME *WindCatalog* [https://wind.nasa.gov/ICME_catalog, 51, 52, 53]. This ICME is characterized by a mean magnetic field strength of 27.95 nT and a velocity of 540 km s^{-1} . The ICME is also listed in the Near-Earth Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections catalog [<https://izw1.caltech.edu/ACE/ASC/DATA/level3/icmetable2.htm>, 62, 61, 9], with mean magnetic field strength of 17 nT and a velocity of 520 km s^{-1} .

Figure 3: COR2-A and C2 coronagraph images of the CME. The 3D CME configuration is shown as derived from the Gradual Cylindrical Shell (GCS) model. The CME has been reported with an angular width $da > 180^\circ$, directed toward Earth.

In Figure 5, we show, from *top* to *bottom*, the STEREO-A time series of: $|B|$ (in *black*) and entropy (in *gray*), $B_X = -B_R$ (in *navy*), $B_Y = -B_T$ (in *cyan*) and B_Z (in *purple*); $|V|$ (in *black*) and N (in *gray*); and the flow (P_{FLOW} , *black*) and magnetic (P_{MAG}). We have changed the radial-tangential-normal components to the GSE coordinate system just for comparison purposes. The *blue* vertical lines indicate the arrival, start and end of the magnetic cloud and end of the ejecta as interpreted by [55].

In both data sets, the magnetic cloud is identified by an enhancement in $|B|$, smooth rotation in the magnetic field components, low density and low temperature, as well as a bump in P_{MAG} [5]. The ICME sheath region exhibits a clear enhancement in P_{FLOW} . The ICME is followed by a fast solar wind stream with a velocity of 550 km s^{-1} . The associated intense geomagnetic storm reached SYM-H values below -200 nT .

Figure 4: Solar wind in situ observations reported by OMNI in Geocentric Solar Ecliptic (GSE) coordinate system during the April 2023 intense geomagnetic storm ($\text{SYM-H} < -200$ nT). From *top to bottom*, the panels show: the magnitude ($|B|$, in *black*) and temperature (T , in *gray*); the components of the magnetic field and velocity (X in *navy*, Y in *cyan*, and Z in *purple*); the magnitude of the velocity ($|V|$, in *black*) and density (N , in *gray*); the flow (P_{FLOW} , in *black*) and magnetic (P_{MAG} , in *navy*) pressures; the SYM-H index (in *black*) and the normalized cosmic ray count rate ($\text{CR}/\text{MAX}(\text{CR})$) from different observatories. The three *purple* vertical lines indicate the arrival (2023 April 23 16:54 UT), start (2023 April 24 00:46 UT) and end (2023 April 24 19:54 UT) times of the magnetic cloud as reported in the ICME *Wind* Catalog.

Figure 5: Solar wind in situ observations by the STEREO-A spacecraft in the GSE coordinate system associated with the April 2023 intense geomagnetic storm. From *top to bottom*, the panels show: the magnitude ($|B|$, in *black*) and entropy (in *gray*); components of the magnetic field (X in *navy*, Y in *cyan*, and Z in *purple*); the magnitude of the velocity ($|V|$, in *black*) and density (N in *gray*), and the flow (P_{FLOW}) and magnetic (P_{MAG}) pressures. The four *blue* vertical lines indicate the arrival (2023 April 23 14:25 UT), start (2023 April 24 23:40 UT) and end (2023 April 25 14:15 UT) times of the magnetic cloud, and the end of the ejecta (2023 April 24 23:00 UT) as reported by [55].

5 The Derivative Analysis - Estimating the *Transient Space*

The derivative analysis is a powerful tool, easy to implement for identifying important transitions between quasi-coherent structures in any time series. The implementation steps are as follows:

STEP 1 Select a time series $\vec{A} = A(t) = \{a_i, a_{i+1}, a_{i+2}, \dots, a_n\}$ of n elements measured by any spacecraft or observatory. As an example, [*] we process the magnitude of the SW velocity from OMNI data, $\vec{A} = \vec{V}$.

STEP 2 Remove data gaps by linear fitting.

STEP 3 Compute the second derivative $\Delta^2 \vec{A} = \frac{\partial^2 \vec{A}}{\partial t^2}$, normalize it as $\mathcal{D}^2 \vec{A} = \Delta^2 \vec{A} / \|\Delta^2 \vec{A}\|$ and take its absolute value $\vec{D}^2 \vec{A} = |\mathcal{D}^2 \vec{A}|$. This yields $\vec{D}^2 \vec{A} = \{d_i, d_{i+1}, d_{i+2}, \dots, d_n\}$ with values ranging from 0 and 1. In our example, we obtain $\vec{D}^2 \vec{V}$.

In Figure 6, we show both \vec{V} and $\vec{D}^2 \vec{V}$. Even at this initial step, the method provides a more accurate arrival time of the ICME, marked by the condition $D^2 V = 1$.

Figure 6: Velocity magnitude (shown in *black*) by OMNI from 2023 April 23 to April 27. In *gray*, we overlap the normalization value of the absolute of its second derivative ($\vec{D}^2 \vec{V}$). STEPS 1, 2, and 3 of the proposed method rely in the estimation of $\vec{D}^2 \vec{V}$. Please note that, in this particular event, the arrival of the solar wind structure is found when $D^2 \vec{V} = 1$.

STEP 4 Define a 200-element array $\sigma = [0.005, 0.01, 0.015, \dots, 1.]$ representing threshold values applied to $\vec{D}^2 \vec{A}$.

STEP 5 Starting with $\sigma_1 = 0.005$, identify periods (\vec{D}_k) where consecutive el-

ements of $\vec{D}^2\vec{A}$ satisfy $\vec{D}^2\vec{A} \leq (\sigma = 0.005)$. \vec{D}_k contains a subset of consecutive indexes $\{i, i + 1, i + 2, \dots, i + j\}$, and a new subset is initiated whenever the condition fails. The index k changes automatically when the condition $d_i \leq \sigma$ does not apply (is false), defining the next k subset.

STEP 6 Create a new array $\mathcal{A}_{\sigma_i} = \vec{A}$. For each subset \vec{D}_k , substitute the corresponding elements in \vec{A} with their median value. In \mathcal{A} substitute the \vec{A}_k elements with the median value of \vec{A} within \vec{A}_k therefore $\mathcal{A}(\vec{A}_k) = (a_i, a_{i+1}, a_{i+2}, \dots, a_{i+j})$.

STEP 7 Repeat steps **5** and **6** for each value of σ .

As an example, Figure 7 shows the time series of $\vec{D}^2\vec{V}$ (*top panel*) with data points satisfying $\vec{D}^2\vec{V} \leq \sigma$ highlighted in *blue*. In this case, $\sigma = 0.075$ represented as the horizontal *blue* line. We also include (*bottom panel*) the original time series of \vec{V} (shown in *black*) compared with the resulting \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} (in *blue*). The median values end up constructing plateaus in the new time series \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} . The plateaus are the k periods where $\vec{D}^2\vec{V} \leq 0.075$ in which the \vec{V}_k elements were substitute by the median value of \vec{V} . In the background of Figure 7, we show \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} in *blue* shades, the color represents the plateau velocity magnitude, slow velocities correspond to *dark blue* while fast velocities to *light blue* shades. The shades help the observation (and determination) of the plateaus.

In Figure 8, we show a second example with $\sigma = 0.175$. The larger the σ the less number of k periods, or else, the duration of some of the plateaus now are longer. The arrival of the CME is still clear in both examples. In the following sections, we discuss how these \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} help identifying different structures in the solar wind still please note the clear distinction between slow and fast solar wind (the transition taking place on 2015 June 23 13:30 UT) as well as the presence of a structure with even faster speed than the surrounding (2015 June 23 16:00 – 18:00 UT).

We repeat this process for all σ values. generating 200 \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} time series represented as shaded *blue* plots.

STEP 8 Construct a matrix $\sigma_{\vec{A}}$ with size $n \times 200$, where each row corresponds to a \mathcal{A}_{σ_i} profile. In this context, a transient is any structure or velocity perturbation propagating through the solar wind. Then, we refer to this matrix as the *transient space* that we plot in *blue* shades allowing the clear distinction of boundaries between solar wind structures, in this case velocity structures with the color transition indicating how slow or fast the structures are propagating. In this example, we define *transient* as any structure or velocity perturbation traveling in the solar wind.

Important information comes when we combine the 200 \mathcal{A}_{σ_i} in one plot. In Figure 9, we show the \vec{V} *transient space* with the original \vec{V} times series (the scale is shown in the *right* Y-axis). In the *left* Y-axis, we scale σ_V , each value is link to the corresponding *blue* shade plot from the previous step representing each \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} . Please note that there are 200 plots condense in the plot background

Figure 7: Plateau construction of the velocity time series selecting $\sigma = 0.075$. *Top* panel: we show the time series $\vec{D}^2 \vec{V}$ coloring in *blue* those data points fulfilling the condition $\vec{D}^2 \vec{V} \leq 0.075$. *Bottom* panel: we show the times series of the velocity in *black* (original time series) with the new one \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} (in *navy*) in which plateaus are found during the k periods where $\vec{D}^2 \vec{V} \leq 0.075$ in which the \vec{V}_k elements were substitute by the median value of \vec{V} . In the background, we show \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} in *blue* shades, *dark blues* represent slow velocity while *light blue* fast velocities. The shades facilitate the observation of the boundaries of the plateaus exiting in \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} .

with the color-bar indicating the velocity values of \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} .

When combined together is possible to notice the differences between \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} . In general, we observe that there are ranges of σ_V which end with similar \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles. Particularly, we note that \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles with $\sigma > 0.3$ split the solar wind in two velocity domains, slow and fast flows. Because of our knowledge of the origin of this flow, these profiles are helping out in the identification of the fast flow originated from the coronal hole. \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles with $\sigma < 0.3$ show a distinctive fast flow from 2015 June 23 16:00 UT to 18:00 UT, in this case, this range corresponds to a high speed coronal mass ejection. Moreover, \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles with $\sigma < 0.2$ is helping with the identification of other velocity structures in the solar wind.

Note that the method provides boundaries which are not relying in the interpretation of the observer but the data itself. The data is giving more information that it seems that would be important to use when analyzing events, in this particular case, solar wind events.

Figure 8: Same information as Figure 7 but for $\sigma = 0.175$. In comparison to Figure 7, we found less number of plateaus (instead some plateaus have longer duration) when filtering the time series.

6 Results

In the previous section, we described the methodology to obtain a *transient space*, that is, a contour plot in which a time series is divided in plateaus based on the temporal behavior of its fluctuations and 200 different threshold values. The method substitutes consecutive time series data points with fluctuation values below the threshold to the median of the data points. This process generates plateaus in the time series. Depending on the threshold, the number of plateaus and their duration is different. Larger threshold values end up in a time series with less number of plateaus and longer duration.

As an example, we obtained the *transient space* of the velocity from OMNI. We show that larger threshold values divides the velocity time series in two regions, slow and fast solar wind while smaller threshold values help identifying large structures traveling within these flows. Particularly, the method identifies a fast coronal mass ejection embedded in the fast flows originated from coronal holes.

Transient spaces can be obtained from any time series of any spacecraft or ground observatory.

To show its versatility, we applied the method to the time series of: WL brightness distributions from C2, C3 and COR-2; the magnitudes of the velocity, magnetic field and density obtained by STEREO-A and OMNI; the SYM-H index; and cosmic ray counts measured by different neutron monitors.

Note that, independently, each *transient space* determines different structure boundaries. Using the velocity, the method provides the times in which

Figure 9: The *transient space* σ_V : a *blue shade* representation of the \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} obtained when choosing the different σ values (200 profiles). The larger the value of σ is, the number of plateaus is reduced and some their duration is lengthen in time. \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles with $\sigma > 0.3$ split the solar wind in slow and fast flow, that way, we identify the flow originated from the coronal hole. \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles with $\sigma < 0.3$ show a distinctive fast flow from 2015 June 23 16:00 UT to 18:00 UT, corresponding to a high speed coronal mass ejection. \mathcal{V}_{σ_i} profiles with $\sigma < 0.2$ is helping with the identification of other velocity structures in the solar wind.

the velocity fluctuations change finding structures based on their speed. The magnetic field *transient space* finds magnetic structures. Each parameter is giving different information.

The data interpretation is even more interesting when we combine the results from different *transient spaces*.

In this section, we show that when using together the *transient spaces* of the density, magnetic field and velocity, we were able to identify the ICME boundaries, their relationship with magnetic clouds and the flows from CHs. We combined the results from OMNI and STEREO-A to show that we identified the MC previously and consistently reported by different authors but also a preceding one compressed by the fast flow originated from a coronal hole and the MC. The compressed magnetic structure is clearly observed in STEREO-A not as compressed as in OMNI showing that the method is potentially helpful when studying structure dynamic and evolution.

We also show that when we combined the *transient space* of the SYM-H with OMNI, we were able to notice transitions related to both MCs as well as the relationship of the time recuperation of the Earth's magnetosphere with the passage of the fast flows originated from the CHs. Moreover, the *spaces* from 32 different ground cosmic ray observatories show clear transitions related to the solar wind structures.

We end this section, by showing that with the *transient spaces* from C2, C3 and COR2-A, we found small CMEs as the source of the compressed MC found in the OMNI and STEREO-A analyses.

We would like to note that, we also investigate the intense geomagnetic storm on 2015 June 22, another very well known and studied event. We present the

observations, the method and corresponding analysis in Lara et al., which is a manuscript that is also part of this special issue.

6.1 Magnetic clouds in the solar wind

Magnetic clouds [MCs, 8, 6, 39] are identified in the solar wind plasma time series because of their: high magnetic field strength, smooth rotation in their magnetic field components and low density. When MCs propagate faster than the surrounding solar wind, they also exhibit a velocity enhancement that gradually decreases (negative slope) back to ambient solar wind conditions. These events are often preceded by density enhancements, as the MC sweeps the ambient solar wind ahead of it. The velocity slope sometimes can be difficult to identify, especially when MCs are followed by other fast structures, such as, other CME or fast flows originated from CHs. But still, the velocity fluctuations within MCs and their preceding compression regions are different [3]. It is also well known that MCs are associated with approximately 50% of major geomagnetic storms reaching $\text{SYM-H} < -100 \text{ nT}$ [86].

The identification of MCs in the solar wind roughly relies on the magnetic field, density and velocity while their geo-effectiveness in the SYM-H. Then, we obtained their *transient spaces*. In Figure 10, we show, from *top to bottom*, the *transient spaces* of the SYM-H (indicating the solar wind geo-effectiveness), the density (pointing out to the preceding compression region and low density signature) magnetic field (magnetic field enhancement) and velocity. *Black* dashed vertical lines show clear transitions which are noticeable in each and all of the *transient spaces*. This is demonstrating that, in general, the fluctuations are correlating different parameters and identifying the same transitions.

The method provides an easy and accurate way to determine the boundaries of different structures that is independently of any interpreter. Based on the *black* dashed vertical lines shown in figure, we can tell a different story of the event than the ones found in previous reports. Its brief version starts with the arrival of a compression region ($t_1 < t < t_2$) resulted from the interaction between the slow solar wind ($t < t_1$) and the fast flows identified at $t > t_1$, that is, the pile up of solar wind. The method clearly identifies a magnetic cloud at $t_3 < t < t_4$. The MC is characterized by its fast velocity (550 km s^{-1}), low density (5 part cm^{-3}), the smooth rotation of the magnetic field and B_Z reaching minimum value of -40 nT . Upon arrival, the MC caused the lowest values of SYM-H of -200 nT within the studied interval. At $t_2 < t < t_3$, we noted a clear structure with $B_Z < -20 \text{ nT}$ in which the velocity, magnetic field and density are considerably enhanced resulting in a SYM-value of -160 nT . These characteristics point out that this structure was compressed by the compression region at $t_2 < t < t_3$ and the MC. Note the smooth behavior of the solar wind at $t_5 < t < t_6$. Within this period, the solar wind is moving at a constant velocity of 550 km s^{-1} barely with a magnetic field strength of 5 nT . This flow seems to be reaching (or interacting with) the MC and causing small velocity, magnetic field and density enhancements ($t_4 < t < t_5$). Both regions, $t_4 < t < t_5$ and $t_5 < t < t_6$ prevent the magnetosphere to recover as it can be noticed by

Figure 10: From *top to bottom*, *transient spaces* and time series of the: SYM-H (σ_{SYM-H} , SYM-H), density (σ_N , N), magnetic field (σ_B , B) with radial R , tangential T and normal N components, and speed (σ_V , B) based on OMNI data. The vertical lines show clear transitions between solar wind structures. The MC previously reported is identified in $t_3 < t < t_4$. With the method, we also identified a compressed MC in $t_2 < t < t_3$.

SYM-H values below -47 nT.

We complement this interpretation by obtaining the *transient spaces* of the density, magnetic field and velocity measured by STEREO-A spacecraft. A quick reference, STEREO-A was separated -11° longitude from Earth. In Figure 11, from *top to bottom*, we show σ_N , σ_B and σ_V . With *black* dashed vertical lines, we marked the relevant transitions. Note that we obtain similar results from those based on OMNI data. Again, we found a compression region at $t_1 < t < t_2$ followed by a small CME at $t_2 < t < t_3$ which is compressed by the MC ($t_3 < t < t_4$) caught up by the fast flow at $t_5 < t < t_6$. Within $t_4 < t < t_5$, we found again signatures of compression with the small density, magnetic field and velocity enhancements. With the method, we were able to directly connect the transitions with those obtained in OMNI, reason why we use the same tags (t_1 , t_2 , etc).

An important difference with OMNI is that we can see clearly the CME signatures of the small CME at $t_2 < t < t_3$. Particularly, we would like to note within this period, the velocity negative slope and magnetic strength of 29 nT.

Few minutes before the arrival of the MC, the method is providing information of a small region in which the magnetic field strength, velocity and density are enhanced pointing out the interaction between both CMEs. At STEREO-A, the small CME was found not as compressed as in OMNI.

Figure 11: From *top to bottom*, *transient spaces* and time series of the: density (σ_N , N), magnetic field (σ_B , B) with the respective R, T, N components and speed (σ_V , V) based on STEREO-A in situ observations. The *black* dashed vertical lines show relevant transitions. Just like in Figure 10, the method helped with the identification of two CMEs and a region with fast flow conditions. We note that the small CME is not as compressed as in OMNI.

From both perspectives, OMNI and STEREO-A observations, we found in the solar wind traces of two CMEs interacting with fast flows. Assuming a velocity of 550 km s^{-1} at t_5 , we roughly estimated a transit time of $75.7 \text{ h} = 3.15 \text{ days}$ connecting the fast flow conditions with the coronal hole discussed in Section 4 and shown in Figure 2.

6.2 Cosmic rays response

The arrival of ICMEs and fast flows originated from coronal holes have been related to decreases in the cosmic ray counts measured by neutron monitors [23, and references therein]. Particularly, it has been found that the minima values of cosmic ray counts is observed upon the arrival of the MCs.

We applied the *transient space* method to cosmic ray count time series obtained from multiple neutron monitor stations. By analyzing fluctuations across a range of thresholds, the technique effectively highlighted periods of modula-

tion linked to interplanetary disturbances such as coronal mass ejections and fast solar wind flows originating from coronal holes. This approach allowed us to detect both prominent and subtle variations in cosmic ray intensity, offering a more nuanced view of space weather impacts of ground-based observations. The consistency of these signatures across geographically diverse stations further validates the robustness of the method.

6.3 Identifying their sources at $10 R_{\odot}$

We applied the derivative-based *transient space* analysis to time series extracted from C2, C3 and COR2-A coronagraph observations, enabling the identification of subtle structural transitions in the white-light data. This approach revealed the presence of small coronal mass ejections that were not easily distinguishable through conventional visual inspection. By tracking fluctuations in brightness profiles across multiple thresholds, the method highlighted coherent eruptive features.

The structure found on 2023 April 21 at 08:00 UT is actually a CME that was observed by Solar Orbiter FSI 174 starting to erupt in the center of the solar disk on 2023 April 21 at 05:20 UT. In Figure 14, we show three snapshots where signatures of eruption are observed (denoted with *violet* rectangles and arrows). At this time Solar Orbiter was above 122° longitude away from the Earth indicating low probability of being geo-effective.

7 Conclusions

In this study, we introduced and applied a novel derivative-base method to construct *transient spaces*, a data-driven approach for identifying boundaries and transitions in solar wind time series. By analyzing fluctuations across multiple thresholds, the method segments time series into plateaus, revealing coherent structures without relying on subjective interpretation.

Using OMNI and STEREO-A observations, we identify two interacting CMEs embedded within fast solar wind flows. The method successfully capture the arrival and evolution of a magnetic cloud, its preceding compression region, and a trailing fast stream, all of which contributed to a prolonged geomagnetic disturbance. The MC was associated with the deepest SYM-H depression (-200 nT) while the compressed region preceding it reached -160 nT, highlighting the geo-effectiveness of both structures. This technique not only captures the internal structure of MCs but also links their arrival to broader space weather impacts.

The *transient space* technique proved versatile across multiple datasets, including velocity, magnetic field, density, SYM-H index, and cosmic ray counts, each revealing distinct but complementary structural boundaries. Notably, the boundaries identified in solar wind parameters were directly correlated with transitions in cosmic ray response. In particular, the arrival of magnetic clouds and fast flows coincided with sharp decreases in cosmic ray counts measured by

ground-based neutron monitors, reinforcing the connection between interplanetary structures and cosmic ray modulation.

When combining *transient spaces* from different observables, we gained a multi-parameter view of solar wind dynamics and their terrestrial impacts. The method revealed a small CME compressed between a coronal hole stream and the magnetic cloud, visible more clearly in STEREO-A than in OMNI, underscoring its potential for studying solar wind evolution across different vantage points.

Finally, we demonstrated the method’s applicability to white-light coronagraph data (C2, c3, COR2-A), linking remote-sensing observations to in-situ signatures. The ability to trace solar wind structures from their origin to their geo-effective impact at Earth, and to connect those boundaries with cosmic ray modulation, opens new avenues for space weather forecasting and solar-terrestrial research.

8 Appendix: Neutron monitors

In Table 1, we show the list of neutron monitor stations used in this study, including their names, geographic (latitude and longitude), and effective vertical cutoff rigidity values (in GV). The cutoff rigidity indicates the minimum energy required for cosmic rays to penetrate Earth’s magnetic field at each location, influencing the station’s sensitivity to galactic cosmic ray variations. More information about the neutron monitor station can be found in the website <https://www.nmdb.eu/station>.

Figures 15, 16, and 17 present the *transient spaces* derived from cosmic ray count time series measured by different neutron monitor stations. Each panel displays the normalized fluctuation profile across varying threshold levels, highlighting periods of reduced cosmic ray intensity. The vertical lines mark key transitions in the solar wind, including the arrival of coronal mass ejections (magnetic clouds), and fast solar wind streams. These transitions align with distinct drops in cosmic ray counts, demonstrating the method’s ability to capture the modulation effects caused by solar wind structures. The consistency of these features across multiple stations reinforces the connection between interplanetary disturbances and ground-based cosmic ray responses.

Figure 12: Cosmic ray count rates and their *transient spaces* derived from cosmic ray count data recorded by the neutron monitor stations: ATHN, NANM, AATB, BKSJ, JUNG, LMKJ, IRK2, and YKTK. The profiles highlight modulation signatures linked to interplanetary disturbances, revealing subtle variations in cosmic ray intensity associated with solar wind structures.

Figure 13: The *transient spaces* constructed from COR2-A coronagraph data at different angles. The derivative-based approach reveals subtle brightness fluctuations associated with small coronal mass ejections, highlighting eruptive features that are otherwise difficult to detect through standard visual inspection.

Figure 14: Snapshots of FSI 174 Å observations obtained by Solar Orbiter. A coronal mass ejection started to erupt on 2023 April 21 at 05:00 UT. This CME is not geo-effective, between Earth and Solar Orbiter there were at least 122° longitude. The *violet* rectangles and arrow are pointing out the region in which the eruption signatures are observed.

Table 1: Neutron monitor stations used in this study, including names, geographic coordinates, and effective vertical cutoff rigidity values (GV), which influence sensitivity to cosmic ray modulation.

Detector	Geographic coordinates	Altitude	Effective vertical
ATHN: Athens, Greece	(37.97°N, 23.78°E)	260 m asl	8.53 GV
NANM: Nor-Amberd, Armenia	(40°22'N, 44°15'E)	2000 m asl	7.1 GV
AATB: Almaty, Kazakhstan	(43.14°N, 76.6°E)	3340 m asl	6.69 GV
BKSN: Troitsk, Russia	(43.28°N, 42.69°E)	1700 m asl	5.6 GV
JUNG: Jungfrauoch, Switzerland	(46.55°N, 7.98°E)	3570 m asl	4.5 GV
LMKS: Lomnický štít, Slovakia	(49.2°N, 20.22°E)	2634 m asl	3.84 GV
IRK2: Irkutsk, Russia	(52.37°N, 100.55°E)	2000 m asl	3.64 GV
YKTK: Yakutsk, Russia	(62.01°N, 129.43°E)	105 m asl	1.65 GV
MXCO: Mexico City, Mexico	(19.33°N, 260.82°E)	2274 m asl	8.2 GV
IRK3: Irkutsk, Russia	(51.29°N, 100.55°E)	3000 m asl	3.64 GV
IRKT: Irkutsk, Russia	(52.47°N, 104.03°E)	475 m asl	3.64 GV
JUNG1: Jungfrauoch, Switzerland	(46.55°N, 7.98°E)	3475 m asl	4.5 GV
DRBS: Dourbes, Belgium	(50.1°N, 4.6°E)	225 m asl	3.18 GV
NEWK: Newark, USA	(39.68°N, 75.75°E)	50 m asl	2.4 GV
KIEL2: Kiel, Germany	(54.34°N, 10.12°E)	54 m asl	2.36 GV
KERG: Kerguelen, Antarctica	(49.35°S, 70.25°E)	33 m asl	1.14 GV
CALG: Calgary, Canada	(51.08°N, 114.13°E)	1123 m asl	1.2 GV
OULU: Oulu, Finland	(65.05°N, 25.47°E)	15 m asl	0.8 GV
APTY: Apatity, Russia	(67.57°N, 33.4°E)	181 m asl	0.65 GV
NRLK: Norilsk, Russia	(69.26°N, 88.05°E)	0 m asl	0.63 GV
TXBY: Tixie Bay, Russia	(71.36°N, 128.54°E)	0 m asl	0.48 GV
FSMT: Fort Smith, Canada	(60.02°N, 111.93°W)	180 m asl	0.3 GV
INVK: Inuvik, Canada	(68.36°N, 133.72°W)	21 m asl	0.3 GV
JBGO: Jang Bogo, Antarctica	(74.6°S, 164.2°E)	30 m asl	0.3 GV
NAIN: Nain, Canada	(56.55°S, 61.68°W)	46 m asl	0.3 GV
PWNK: Peawanuck, Canada	(54.98°N, 85.44°W)	53 m asl	0.3 GV
THUL: Thule, Greenland	(76.5°N, 68.7°W)	26 m asl	0.3 GV
SOPB: South Pole Bares, Antarctica	(90°S, N/A)	2820 m asl	0.1 GV
SOPO: South Pole, Antarctica	(90°S, N/A)	2820 m asl	0.1 GV
DOMB: Concordia, Antarctica	(75°06'S, 123°20'E)	3233 m asl	< 0.01 GV
DOMC: Concordia, Antarctica	(75°06'S, 123°20'E)	3233 m asl	0.01 GV
TERA: Terre Adelie, Antarctica	(66.65°06'S, 140°20'E)	32 m asl	0 GV

Figure 15: Cosmic ray counts and their *transient spaces* derived from neutron monitor stations: MXCO, IKR3, IRKT, JUNG1, DRBS, NEWK, KIEL2, and KERG. These profiles highlight modulation signatures associated with solar wind structures and interplanetary disturbances.

Figure 16: Same format as Figure 15 but showing *transient spaces* of cosmic ray counts for neutron monitor stations: CALG, OULU, APTY, NRLK, TXBY, FSMT, INVK, and JBGO.

Figure 17: Same format as Figures 15 and 16 now showing *transient spaces* of cosmic ray counts for neutron monitor stations: NAIN, PWNK, THUL, SOPB, SOPO, DOMB, DOMC, and TERA.

Open Research Section

The study utilized publicly accessible neutron monitor and solar wind datasets, retrieved from the NMDB (www.nmdb.eu) and NASA's CDAWeb portal (<https://cdaweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/>) to investigate solar wind structures and cosmic ray modulation.

For solar imaging and event tracking, we employed JHelioviewer [49], an open-source visualization tool developed by the ESA JHelioviewer Team.

Additionally, the catalog of Near-Earth Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections (ICME) Catalog is freely available through [62]. The Wind ICME catalog used in this study is openly available through the website: https://wind.nasa.gov/ICME_catalog/ICME_catalog_viewer.php.

Visualization and data analysis were performed using IDL and Python 3.13.2, incorporating the following packages: NumPy [?], version 1.26.4, SciPy [?], version 1.13.1 and Sunpy version 6.1.1 [71] part of the open source software suite [50].

Conflict of Interest disclosure

The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest for this manuscript.

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cosmic ray NM by the Institute of Ionosphere, Kazakhstan; BKSJ: BAKSAN NM by Institute of Nuclear Physics Russian Academy of Sciences; JUNG and JUNG1: Jungfrauoch NMs by the Physikalisches Institut, University of Bern, Switzerland; LMKŠ Lomnický štít NM by Slovak grant agency APVV, project no. 51-053805; IRK2: Irkutsk2, IRK3: Irkutsk3 and IRKT: Irkutsk NMs by the Institute of Solar-Terrestrial Physics Russian Academy of Sciences; YKTK: YAKUTSK NM by the Institute of Cosmophysical Research and Aeronomy of Russian Academy of Science; MXCO: Mexico City NM by the Grupo de Rayos C3smicos, Instituto de Geofísica, Universidad Nacional Aut3noma de M3xico; DRBS: Dourbes MN by the Royal Meteorological Institute of Belgium; NEWK: Newark NM by the University of Delaware Department of Physics and Astronomy and the Bartol Research Institute; KIEL2: Kiel NM by the Extraterrestrial Physics Department of the Institute for Experimental and Applied Physics of the Christian-Albrechts University of Kiel; KERG: Kerguelen NM by Observatoire de Paris and the French polar institute (IPEV), France; CALG: Calgary NM by University of Calgary; OULU: Oulu NM by Sodankyla Geophysical Observatory of the University of Oulu; APTY: APATITY NM is operated by Polar Geophysical Institute Russian Academy of Sciences; NRLK: NORILSK MN by Institute of Solar-Terrestrial Physics (ISZF, Irkutsk), Russian Academy of Sciences; TXBY: TIXIE NM by the Institute of Cosmophysical Research and Aeronomy of Russian Academy of Science; FSMT: Fort Smith NM by the University of Delaware Department of Physics and Astronomy and the Bartol Research Institute; INVK, Inuvik NM by the University of Delaware Department of Physics and Astronomy and the Bartol Research Institute; JBGO: Jang Bogu NM by the Chonnam National University; NAIN: Nain NM by the University of Delaware Department of Physics and Astronomy and the Bartol Research Institute; PWNK: Peawanuck NM by the University of Delaware Department of Physics and Astronomy and the Bartol Research Institute; THUL: Thule NM by the University of Delaware Department of Physics and Astronomy and the Bartol Research Institute; SOPB: South Pole Bares and SOPO: South Pole NMs by the University of Wisconsin, River Falls; DOMB and DOMC: Dome NMs by Sodankylä Geophysical Observatory (University of Oulu, Finland); TERA: Terre Adelie NM by Observatoire de Paris and the French polar institute (IPEV), France. T.N. would like to thank K. Paulson, and S. Badman for helpful discussions while we carried out the analysis for this manuscript.

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